

Entropy and Lost Information

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In (1) it is suggested that Shannon's entropy - $\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ be thought of as the average of lost information defined by $\ln(P(i))$. To see why the function \ln appears, it seems one needs to consider a product of probabilities: $P=P(i)P(j)$. It is possible that another two probabilities k,l yield the same product probability $P(k)P(l)=P$. In such a case, given P one would not know which two probabilities created it. For a specific instance, however, one specifically knows $P(i)$ and $P(j)$ and so "information" so to speak is lost through the product. To describe information as a quantity which "adds" one may take \ln i.e. $\ln(P)=\ln(P(i)) + \ln(P(j)) = \ln(P(k)) + \ln(P(l))$ with $\ln(P(i))$ being information. The above is established for only two probabilities, but a $P(i)P(j)$ result suggests two independent "coin tosses" so to speak or roll of a die. As a result, there seems to be a generalization in the literature to N successive independent events with N being large or a series of arrangements of results making use of Stirling's approximation. Stirling's approximation depends on large N and so this approach suggests that Shannon's entropy holds for a large number of events. We have argued above that if considered as a loss of entropy (1), one only needs a product of two events.

It is possible that one does not even need two successive events such as the toss of a coin or a die. For a quantum bound state, a product of probabilities $P(x)P(p/x)$ appears if one wishes to know the probability for a particle to be at x and have p . In general this is not allowable in quantum mechanics so $P(p/x)$ is complex. It is possible to have different (x,p) pairs yield the same $P(x)P(p/x)$ product so lost information would be: $\ln\{ \sum_p |a(p)\exp(ipx)/W|^2 \}$ yielding an entropy of $S=S_p+S_x$ where S_p and S_x are Shannon's entropy for p and x . Thus the idea of successive events or arrangements is not needed, rather entropy deals with a loss of information through a product of probabilities as argued in (1).

One may also have a loss of information through a sum of probabilities, but in such a case \ln does not isolate the pieces of lost information. In physical systems, however, it seems that products of probabilities appear especially due to two body scattering or to an energy level absorbing a photon. The idea of sum then appears through a conserved quantity such as energy or momentum which dictates the form of $P(i)$.

Lost Information

In (1) it is suggested that entropy is linked to lost information which is defined as $\ln(P(i))$. In fact, Shannon's entropy is then understood as the average of this lost information:

$$S_{\text{Shannon}} = - \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i)) \quad ((1))$$

This begs the question: Why is information given by $\ln(P(i))$? For example, one might consider $P=P(i)+P(j)=P(k)+P(l)$. In such a case, one begins with knowledge about two states i,j or k,l , but loses that knowledge in the sum. There is thus a loss of information, but no \ln function.

In many examples, probability is verified through repeated events. For example if told that a coin has an equal likelihood to produce heads or tails upon a toss, one would toss the coin

successively. This leads to various sets of arrangements each with a product probability $\prod_i P(i)$. To prove that a coin has equal probability for heads and tails, one would toss it N times with N being large. In such a case, one would expect $N P(\text{heads})$ and $N(1-P(\text{heads}))$ tails. For a die one would have $N P(i)$ where i may be 1 to 6 and $P(i)=\frac{1}{6}$. The product probability of any arrangement of large N tosses is expected to be:

$$P = \prod_i P(i)^{N P(i)} \quad ((2))$$

One cannot use $N P(i)$ unless N is very large. Taking \ln of both sides of ((2)) and setting $P=1/N$ (total number of arrangements) yields $\ln(\text{arrangements}) = - \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ or Shannon's entropy. This approach then suggests that the number of arrangements is a key idea and that N must be large. Shannon's entropy then follows.

Given that many physical processes are linked to sequences, one may obtain $\ln(P(i))$ without large N by thinking of loss of information. Consider $P=P(i)P(j)$. It is possible that for another set (k,l) $P=P(k)P(l)$. In such a case, given P , one cannot distinguish between the two sets (i,j) and (k,l) . Information is lost because one originally knows $P(i)$ and $P(j)$ or $P(k)$ and $P(l)$, but then no longer does given P . In such a case taking \ln yields:

$$\ln(P) = \ln(P(i)) + \ln(P(j)) \quad ((3))$$

No arrangements are used and no large N limit either, all that is required is a physical reason for taking a product of probabilities. One may find the average of lost information through: $-\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$. This in (1) it is suggested that entropy be associated with lost information.

Physical Interactions Which are Linked to Loss of Information

Above we considered products of probabilities linked to repeated stochastic events such as the tossing of a coin or die. In physical systems with numerous particles there are often interactions which impose a product of probabilities and lead to information loss. For example, consider two body scattering in an ideal gas (or three or more body scattering) as long as the reaction is elastic. In such a case, $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. There is a loss of information in a physically conserved quantity namely overall energy of reactants. Any i and j which yield $e_i+e_j=E$ are equally satisfactory. The probability to have an e_1 and e_2 collide is assumed to be given by:

$$P(e_1)P(e_2) = P \quad ((4))$$

If the reaction is time reversible $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3)P(e_4)$ ((5)). If one thinks of loss of information, however, the product $P(e_1)$ relative $P(e_2)$ (relative) seen by the interaction is simply :

$$P_{\text{relative}}(e_1+e_2) \quad ((5))$$

The interaction does not distinguish between e_1 's and e_2 's. Thus in this case a loss of information in the interaction i.e. the elastic constraint constrains the form of the probability namely:

$$P(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)/C(T) \quad ((6))$$

To consider lost information, one performs $\ln(P(e_1)P(e_2)) = \ln(P(e_1)) + \ln(P(e_2))$. Again there is no sequence or set of arrangements with N large. The information is linked to e_1+e_2 so forming E_{ave} and S the average of information leads to:

$$E_{ave} - TS = -T \ln(C(T)) \quad ((7))$$

where the RHS is free energy in thermodynamics.

A second case in which a physical conservation law which loses information leads to the form of a probability is in a quantum bound state. Momentum is conserved in both classical and quantum mechanics. If a free quantum particle with momentum p receives an impulse hit of momentum k from a potential, the overall momentum is $p+k$. If there is a probability to have $P_{special}(p)$ and $P_{special}(k)$ then:

$$P_{special}(p) P_{special}(k) = P_{special}(p+k) \quad ((8))$$

The reason we have written $P_{special}$ is that the variable x also appears in the picture. A classical potential is of the form $V(x)$ and it accelerates a particle at x . It does not give a momentum hit based on a probability. If one considers momentum hits they must not depend in particular on x in a fashion biased to high or low x values, but must still depend on x because on average they must reproduce $V(x)$. The average, however, is unusual in that it involves interference. This is linked to distinguishing the hits over a global range instead of $V(x)$ at a local point. Assuming p_x (and there are various reasons for this), ((8)) becomes:

$$P(p_x)P(k_x) = P((p+k)_x) \quad \text{or} \quad P(p_x) = \exp(ip_x) \quad \text{so that there is no bias to high or low } x \quad ((9))$$

This is an unusual probability in that it is (A) complex and (B) mixes p and x . $\exp(ip_x)$, however, represents an orthogonal basis, so different p states are distinguished globally overall x i.e. $\langle \exp(ip_1 x) | \exp(ip_2 x) \rangle = \delta(p_1, p_2)$.

Taking \ln yields:

$P_{x+k_x} = (p+k)_x$ which is the conservation result. Thus this is a second example in which a loss of information, which is built into the particular reaction in question, dictates the form of a probability.

In general, however, this is not the case. For the toss of a coin, $\ln(1/2)$ or for a die $\ln(1/6)$ is not equivalent to a quantity in a reaction it seems. Again there is no scenario of arrangements or large N .

Bound Quantum State

In the above, one considered $P(i)P(j)$ products, with $P(i)$ representing like events. For example $P(\text{heads})$, $P(\text{tails})$ are linked to outcomes of a coin toss. $P(e_i)$ and $P(e_j)$ are probabilities linked to the state of a particle, quantum or classical. If interactions occur a particle may change from $P(e_1)$ to $P(e_2)$ to $P(e_3)$ in time and so one might think of arrangements.

For a quantum bound state, one may have a product of probabilities which do not deal with the same variable. For example, one may have:

$P(x)P(p/x)$ where $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ and $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ where $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p$
 $a(p)\exp(ipx) = \text{wavefunction}$

It is possible that two sets (x_1, p_1) and (x_2, p_2) yield the same product $P(x)P(p/x)$. In such a case there is again information loss because given the product probability, one does not know which set one has. As a result one may take:

$\ln(P(x)P(p/x)) = \ln(W(x) a(p) \exp(ipx))$ as information which leads to the entropy (information average) $S = S_p + S_x$ with S_p and S_x being Shannon's entropies with $P(p)=a(p)a(p)$ and $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ for bound states ((10))

Alternatively, one may consider the product $P(p)P(x/p) = a(p)a(p) W(x) \exp(-ipx)/a(p)$ (bound state)

Typically in the literature one considers p and x separately and so there is no product $P(x)P(p/x)$. In such a case, one must consider successive values of p_i for p linked to $P(p_i)P(p_j)P(p_k)$ etc and then consider a loss of information in the product. This leads to S_p standing on its own. Similarly S_x stands on its own.

Thus it seems that one is moving away from the notion of arrangements and large N and yet still as a \ln form in entropy if one thinks of it as a loss of information as suggested in (1).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider entropy in terms of an average of loss of information with information given by $\ln(P(i))$ as suggested in (1). This leads to the form of Shannon's entropy. We suggest that the \ln form makes sense if one has products of probability e.g. $P(i)P(j)=P$. Given a P value, there might be another set $P(k)P(l)$ which yields the same P and so there is a loss of information. If one wishes to have information represented by an additive quantity, then $\ln(P(i)) + \ln(P(j)) = \ln(P)$ satisfies this requirement. This, however, does not cover all cases of loss of information as $P(i)+P(j)=P$ also contains loss, but one does not use \ln .

We note that in nature there are reactions which lose information. For example for elastic scattering $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l$. Any (i,j) and (k,l) pairs are on the same footing as long as $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l$. There is information loss because there is initial knowledge of e_i and e_j , but the reaction only "senses" the sum. This has consequences on the probabilities $P(e_i)$ because it is assumed that

an e_i+e_j reaction is linked to $P(e_i)P(e_j)$. The reaction cannot distinguish between e_i and e_j , only the sum, so $P_{\text{relative}}(e_i) P_{\text{relative}}(e_j) = P_{\text{relative}}(e_i+e_j)$ and $P(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T)/C(T)$. Similarly for a quantum bound state momentum is conserved so one $P(p_x)=\exp(ip_x)$. (For more details see above.) In general, however, $\ln(P(i))$ is not linked to a conserved quantity e.g. $\ln(P(i))$ for a coin toss or die is simply \ln of a probability.

We argue that the notion of arrangements and large N , although they exist, are not necessary for creating $\ln(P(i))$ as information. All that is necessary is the notion of products of probabilities appearing with a loss of information through the product. It is not the case that the scenario of large N and arrangements give a wrong result. They yield Shannon's entropy, but we argue one may obtain it directly through the idea of loss of information as suggested in (1) without arrangements or large N . (We have suggested in another note that one may also obtain the form $S = -\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$ if one wishes to have a dS (created through changes $dP(i)$) such that $\sum_i dP(i)=0$, be proportional to the dot product of a constant vector $\{F(P(i))\}$ with the vector $\{dP(i)\}$.)

In particular, we consider a quantum bound state with $P(x)P(p/x)$ which yields a probability to have p and x (which is complex because there is not a real probability for this in quantum mechanics). Different (x,p) pairs may yield the same product so $\ln(P(x)P(p/x)) = \ln(W a(p) \exp(ipx))$ is information and $S = S_p+S_x$ with S_p and S_x being Shannon's entropies with $P(p)=a(p)a(p)$ and $P(x) = WW$ for a bound state.

References

1. Lent, C. Information and Entropy in Physical Systems (U. of Notre Dame 2018 or later) https://www3.nd.edu/~lent/pdf/nd/Information_and_Entropy_in_Physical_Systems.pdf